

LINKING PROCESS MODELLING WITH STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATED PLATES USING LAYERWISE THEORY

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Abstract

In this study a methodology is introduced to integrate process modelling of a composite structure with its nonlinear damage modelling in a seamless manner within a common computational analysis framework. The methodology which has been implemented in the commercial finite element software, ABAQUS, through a user-coded element links our previously developed process modelling approach, COMPRO Component Architecture (CCA), with the composite damage modelling approach, CODAM. A simple numerical example is presented to illustrate the effect of process-induced residual stresses on promoting the initiation of damage in a cross-ply composite laminate subjected to a uniaxial tensile load.

1 Introduction

The use of polymer matrix composite materials (PMC) has become increasingly common in load bearing components of aircraft structures. A crucial problem in the application of PMCs in structural components is the presence of high levels of residual stresses induced during the manufacturing process. It is crucial that designers understand how the process-induced residual stresses affect the structural behaviour under different loading conditions and thereby take into account the as-manufactured conditions of the structure in their analysis/design. The goal of this research endeavour is to seamlessly link process modelling with the in-service structural analysis of composite structures using the same finite element modelling framework.

There are several phenomena that are responsible for

the build-up of residual stresses during the manufacturing process of composites including mechanical tool-part interaction, through-thickness gradients in the degree of cure, and anisotropic thermo-chemical strains [1].

The level of process-induced residual stresses can be sufficiently high to cause damage in the material during the manufacturing process, or accelerate the formation and growth of cracks during the service conditions. Prediction of the residual stresses and the consequential formation of damage/defect during the curing process is challenging since multiple mechanisms interact at the same time.

Three-dimensional solid elements are commonly employed to model process-induced residual stresses since classical shell elements are not able to accurately capture the highly nonlinear through-thickness stress gradients and the stresses due to material anisotropy. Solid elements are also necessary to evaluate the through-thickness stresses of a part accurately for damage analysis including delamination.

However, the main drawback of using solid elements is that a rather large number of such elements are often necessary to satisfy accuracy requirements while avoiding the locking effect that occurs in solid elements with large aspect ratios. In recent years, many shell-like solid element formulations have been reported in the literature, with the intent of eliminating the locking effects [2-3]. Even though these elements allow large aspect ratios, one still needs to employ more than one element through the thickness to capture the large

stress gradients induced during manufacturing process [3-4] and the transverse stresses through the thickness of the part during the in-service loading conditions. The number of elements needed through the thickness varies depending on the lay-up, loading conditions, etc., and is usually determined by trial-and-error, which is ineffective and costly.

Adaptive mesh refinement has been the subject of extensive investigation [6-7]. The two main categories of refinements are the h-refinement and the p-refinement. The Layer-wise theory, proposed by Reddy for composite structures [8-9], is an example of h-refinement. It was shown [4] that the h-refinement method (layer-wise element) is more efficient than the p-refinement method in predicting process-induced stresses.

2 Layer-wise Element

In this study, a previously developed element [4-5] based on the layer-wise theory has been modified to model both the curing process and the in-service behaviour of a composite structure.

In the layer-wise element approach, the basic element has 24-nodes in total (8 on each of the bottom, top and mid planes) as shown in Fig. 1. The bottom and top surface nodes have the 3 conventional displacement d.o.f's (u , v and w). The number of d.o.f's at the mid-plane nodes varies depending on the number of element-layers used implicitly in the layer-wise technique. The d.o.f's at the mid-plane nodes correspond to the displacements in the various element layers through the thickness. The through-thickness shape function for such an element is quadratic. An additional element-layer can be added to the element by introducing two more nodes in the thickness direction as shown in Fig. 2. To add physical nodes, a new mesh needs to be generated. However, to avoid mesh regeneration, an element layer can be added through the introduction of additional d.o.f's at the mid-nodes.

The layer-wise element was implemented in the commercial finite element software, ABAQUS, as a user-defined element and was successfully used to predict process-induced warpage of flat unidirectional composite plates [4-5].

3 Process Modelling Framework

Autoclave processing of composite structures consists of many complex physical phenomena such as heat transfer, resin flow and stress development. Due to the complexities involved in modelling, composite processing has generally been modelled using the 'integrated sub-module' approach [1]. Based on this approach, a complex problem of process modelling is divided into three simpler sub-modules: Thermo-chemical, flow-compaction and stress-deformation sub-modules. These sub-modules can be studied more or less independently. Our focus in this study is the stress-deformation sub-module.

The concept of COMPRO component architecture (CCA) was developed to analyse the process-induced stresses and deformation of composite structures during manufacturing using commercial finite element software [5]. The basic CCA module is shown in Fig. 3. At each time step, the state variables; namely, temperature (T), degree of cure (α) and fibre volume fraction (V_f) from the previous time step are passed into CCA and updated. Based on the new state variables, the thermo-mechanical properties of the fibre and the resin are calculated. The micromechanics module calculates the composite properties from the updated properties of the fibre and the resin and the fibre volume fraction at that point using micro-mechanics equations.

The stress-deformation sub-module is responsible for predicting strains and stresses in the material based on the given incremental strains. This module is based on the *cure-hardening instantaneously linear elastic* (CHILE) model [1].

$$\Delta\sigma = \mathbf{D} \Delta\epsilon^{mech} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\epsilon^{mech}$ is the incremental mechanical strain, \mathbf{D} is the instantaneous stiffness matrix and $\Delta\sigma$ is the incremental stress at a given integration point. In the time step analysis, the total residual stress at the current time t_n , is calculated by adding up all the incremental stresses from the beginning of the curing process to the end of the n^{th} time step:

$$\sigma_n = \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta\sigma_i \quad (2)$$

4 Damage Modelling Framework

The UBC Composite Damage Model (CODAM) which was first introduced by Williams et. al. [10] is a physically-based model intended to simulate the effect of damage on stiffness reduction at the sub-laminate level. The formulation of CODAM was later modified and extended by Forghani [11] to address the material and computational objectivity issues that were present in the original model. Similar to its predecessor, this second generation of the UBC Composite Damage Model, CODAM2, homogenizes the damage behaviour of the laminate at a length scale which considers a stack of layers representing a repeating unit of the laminate or sub-laminate. This is considered to be the minimum scale of resolution needed to account for the damage interactions among the various layers.

CODAM2 reduces the in-plane stiffness of the layers as a result of matrix cracking and fibre breakage and uses the classical lamination theory to calculate the stiffness of the sub-laminate.

The damaged in-plane stiffness matrix of the k^{th} ply, \mathbf{Q}_k^d , can be written as

$$\mathbf{Q}_k^d = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{R_f E_1}{1 - R_f R_m \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} & \frac{R_f R_m \nu_{12} E_2}{1 - R_f R_m \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{R_m E_2}{1 - R_f R_m \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} & \frac{R_m E_2}{1 - R_f R_m \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} & 0 \\ SYM & & R_m G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where R_f and R_m are the fibre and matrix stiffness reduction coefficients, respectively. E_1 , E_2 and G_{12} are longitudinal, transverse and shear moduli; and ν_{12} and ν_{21} are the major and minor Poisson's ratios.

Fibre and matrix stiffness reduction factors (R_f and R_m) are assumed to vary as a linear function of the fibre and matrix damage parameters, ω_f and ω_m as follows:

$$\begin{cases} R_f = 1 - \omega_f \\ R_m = 1 - \omega_m \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In CODAM2, equivalent strain parameters, which are functions of the total strain, govern the growth of damage.

The equivalent strain for matrix damage, ϵ_m^{eq} , is defined as a function of the transverse normal and shear strains, and the equivalent strain for fibre damage, ϵ_f^{eq} , is equal to the strain along the fibre direction:

$$\epsilon_m^{eq} = \text{sign}(\epsilon_{22}) \sqrt{(\epsilon_{22})^2 + \left(\frac{\gamma_{12}}{2}\right)^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon_f^{eq} = \epsilon_{11}$$

The damage parameters are written as hyperbolic functions of the equivalent strain as shown schematically in Fig. 4.

In modelling composite laminated plate with a 3D layered element, each integration point represents one of the layers in the sub-laminate.

$$\bar{\mathbf{Q}}_k^d = \mathbf{T}^T \mathbf{Q}_k^d \mathbf{T} \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{Q}}_k^d$ is the damaged stiffness matrix of the k^{th} layer in the global coordinate system and \mathbf{T} is the standard transformation (rotation) matrix for the strain vector.

5 Linking Process Simulation and Damage Modelling

In the combined approach, first, the CCA is used to determine the material stiffness and stresses of the undamaged material as they evolve during processing. CODAM2 is subsequently used to quantify damage, if any, and perform the corresponding stiffness reductions and stress computations.

As outlined in Section 3, at each time-step in the CHILE approach the incremental mechanical strains arising from the applied external load and thermo-chemical strains generated in the material during the process are used to calculate the stress increments. However, CODAM2 uses the total strain as a basis to calculate the secant stiffness of the damaged material.

The total strain calculated by summing up the mechanical strain increments during the curing process does not have a physical meaning given that each increment of mechanical strain is associated

with a different state of the material as curing advances and therefore the material stiffness evolves. Physically, the quantity that better represents the state of the material for the purposes of damage modelling is the accumulated stress, i.e. the stresses that are computed using Equation (2).

To address this issue of incompatibility between the process and damage modelling approaches, an *effective mechanical strain* parameter is defined as

$$\hat{\epsilon} = (\mathbf{Q}^0)^{-1} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^0 \quad (7)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^0$ is the current stress calculated from the processing model and \mathbf{Q}^0 is the current stiffness of the undamaged material. It should be noted that $\hat{\epsilon}$ is a fictitious quantity and does not represent the real state of strain in the material. It is merely the strain equivalence of the current state of stress in the material. In other words, $\hat{\epsilon}$ is the mechanical strain that would have resulted in a state of stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^0$, in a virtual, linear elastic material with constant stiffness \mathbf{Q}^0 . The damage model is then formulated on the basis of the above-defined effective mechanical strain thus retaining the advantages of continuum damage mechanics formulations in the strain space.

5.1 Algorithm

At the beginning of each time increment, the incremental displacements $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ in an element are computed leading to the calculation of the incremental strains using the standard strain-displacement relationship as follows:

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \mathbf{B} \Delta \mathbf{u} \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ includes the contributions from both mechanical and thermo-chemical (thermal expansion and resin cure shrinkage) strains. To compute the incremental mechanical strains, the free thermal and cure shrinkage strains, $\Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{ther}$, obtained from the thermo-chemical module, need to be subtracted:

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{mech} = \Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon} - \Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{ther} \quad (9)$$

Then the incremental effective stress (in absence of damage) is calculated:

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}^0 = \mathbf{Q}^0 \Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{mech} \quad (10)$$

According to the CHILE model, the material is assumed to be linear elastic in each increment of time and \mathbf{Q}^0 is the undamaged material stiffness at the current increment.

The total effective stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^0$ is then calculated by accumulating the incremental stresses up to the current time step and used to compute the effective mechanical strain from Equation (7).

This effective mechanical strain, $\hat{\epsilon}$ is then used to update the fibre and matrix damage parameters based on the CODAM2 formulation. The damage parameters are then used to calculate the appropriate stiffness reduction factors which in turn act on the current undamaged stiffness matrix computed from the stress-deformation sub-module to obtain the damaged stiffness matrix (\mathbf{Q}^d).

The stresses are then calculated as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{Q}^d \hat{\epsilon} \quad (11)$$

Finally, the stress vector and damaged stiffness matrix ($\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and \mathbf{Q}^d) at all integration points of the element are used to compute the element stiffness matrix and internal nodal force vector that are then passed to the main FE solver.

5.2 Pseudo-Code

The following describes the various computational steps involved in a given time step.

- Loop through in-plane integration points ($i = 1$ to 2 and $j = 1$ to 2)
- Obtain in-plane local coordinates of the integration point (ξ_i, η_j) .
- Loop through thickness integration points in the layers ($k = 1$ to n).
- Obtain through-thickness local coordinate (ξ_k) .
- Call subroutine *TEMPERATURE* to calculate the temperature at this integration point.
- Call CCA subroutine to calculate the undamaged stiffness matrix, \mathbf{Q}^0 , and incremental thermal strain vector $\Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{ther}$.
- Call subroutine *B_MATRIX* to calculate the *B* matrix.
- Calculate the incremental strain vector

$$\Delta \epsilon = B \Delta u.$$

- Calculate the incremental mechanical strain $\Delta \epsilon^{mech} = \Delta \epsilon - \Delta \epsilon^{ther}$.
- Calculate the incremental effective stress $\Delta \sigma^0 = Q^0 \Delta \epsilon^{mech}$
- Update the total effective stress $\sigma_{t+\Delta t}^0 = \sigma_t^0 + \Delta \sigma^0$
- Calculate the total effective strain $\hat{\epsilon} = (Q^0)^{-1} \sigma^0$
- Call subroutine *DAMAGE* to update the damage parameters and stiffness matrix Q^d based on $\hat{\epsilon}$.
- Calculate the stress $\sigma = Q^d \hat{\epsilon}$
- Calculate the element secant stiffness matrix and the internal nodal force vector and pass to the main FE solver for the next increment.

6 Numerical Example

A simple numerical example is presented to illustrate the effect of process-induced residual stresses on damage initiation of a composite plate using the developed framework.

A cross-ply, carbon fibre-reinforced plastic (CFRP) composite laminate with a span of 102mm, a width of 9.75mm and a thickness of 1.14mm is considered for this study. The plate is made of Hexply AS4/8552 material with $[0/90_2]_s$ lay-up.

First the composite plate was virtually cured on a rigid invar tool (Fig. 5) in an autoclave using two different cure cycles as shown in Fig. 6. Then the cured plates were removed from the tool and subjected to external load (applied displacement) as shown in Fig. 7 to analyse the damage initiation. Due to symmetry, only a quarter of the plate was modelled.

At the end of the cure cycle, the process-induced stresses in the transverse (90 degree) ply in the longitudinal direction (i.e. loading direction) of the laminate cured with a 1-hold and 2-hold cure cycles (shown in Fig. 6) are 38 MPa and 42 MPa, respectively. With the initiation strain for fibre and matrix damage assumed to be 1.1% and 0.8%, respectively, no damage was initiated during the curing process.

To better illustrate the effect of matrix damage on

the stiffness of the laminate and locate the point where damage initiates, the derivative of the applied force with respect to displacement as a function of the applied displacement is plotted in Fig. 8. The figure compares the damage initiation of an as-designed part with that of the as-manufactured part that includes the effect of process-induced residual stresses due to the two different cure cycles. As shown in the figure, the damage initiation starts much earlier in the as-manufactured laminate that accounts for the process-induced stresses than that in the as-designed laminate. The figure also shows that the damage initiation may significantly vary based on the cure cycle used for manufacturing.

7 Conclusions

In this study, a methodology has been introduced to link the numerical simulation of the manufacturing process of composites with their nonlinear damage modelling during in-service loading conditions. A solid-like shell element based on the layer-wise approach was employed to combine both process and damage simulations in one single finite element modelling framework thus eliminating the need to create separate meshes for process modelling and structural analysis. A simple numerical example was presented to illustrate the effect of process-induced residual stresses on damage initiation in a composite structure during its service life.

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Fig. 1 – The 24-node hierarchical solid element

Fig. 2 - Through-thickness displacement interpolation functions for layer-wise elements: (a) one-layer, and (b) two-layer elements

Fig. 3 - The COMPRO Component Architecture (CCA)

developed to incorporate the composite behaviour during cure in a commercial finite element code [5]

Fig. 4 - Damage parameter as a function of the equivalent strain

Fig. 5 - Schematic of the composite plate on a rigid invar tool

Fig. 6 - Two different cure cycles used in the process simulation of the composite laminate

Fig. 7 - Schematic of the composite plate with applied uniaxial tensile displacement

Fig. 8 – In-plane laminate stiffness (derivative of applied force with respect to displacement) as a function of the applied displacement for the as-designed laminate as well as the as-manufactured laminate with two different cure cycles

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